

StarQuantrol: FPGA-Based Quantum-Inspired Reaction Wheel Control

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Abstract—CubeSats and flagship observatories like Hubble and James Webb require precise attitude control systems and efficient computation. StarQuantrol proposes an FPGA-based reaction wheel platform with emulated quantum-inspired control, comparing conventional PID controllers with quantum-emulated algorithms in orientation accuracy, signal robustness, and autonomous decision-making.

I. MOTIVATION

CubeSats and flagship observatories like Hubble and James Webb Space Telescope necessitate precise attitude control systems as well as fast, reliable, and efficient computation. Such demanding control tasks require reaction wheels, which provide a proven foundation for benchmarking against new control methods. These tasks are primarily offloaded on conventional controllers, such as PIDs; however, they struggle under the microgravity disturbances of satellite missions, the non-linear dynamics of the environment, and the limited network bandwidth during flights [1], [2].

A promising alternative to PID controllers is modeling the physical dynamics of the reaction wheel as a set of differential equations and formulating the control problem as optimization. These optimizations can alleviate the limitations of typical PID controllers, as they are computationally intractable for classical methods.

Meanwhile, quantum computing offers a powerful alternative for such computationally heavy tasks. Parallelism and superposition in quantum computing introduce stochastic and adaptive strategies to optimize routines needed to perform control on the system. Specifically, quantum-inspired control algorithms like Variational Quantum Circuits (VQCs) alleviate the inefficiencies of typical controllers by providing adaptive and stochastic control.

Nevertheless, the advanced complexity of these algorithms requires the use of quantum hardware, which is prohibitive on satellite missions due to budget and stability constraints [3], [4].

A promising alternative is to integrate embedded FPGA platforms on satellite missions, which demonstrate efficient and capable emulation of quantum algorithms, even in advanced fields like defense satellites [4]. FPGAs eliminate the shortcomings of quantum hardware as they offer a unique combination of compute and power efficiency, allowing the system to be adapted to the tight constraints of space missions.

To bridge the best of both worlds, we present StarQuantrol, an FPGA-based reaction wheel platform with emulated quantum-inspired control. By leveraging quantum-classical algorithms, the system aims to compare conventional control algorithms with quantum emulated ones (VQC), in terms of orientation accuracy, signal robustness and autonomous decision-making.

II. ESSENTIAL BACKGROUND

A. Reaction Wheel

Importance: Reaction wheels are among the most used attitude control systems for satellites and space telescopes because they provide precise and continuous control of orientation.

Operation: Reaction wheels operate based on the conservation of angular momentum. When the reaction wheel accelerates in one direction, the platform or satellite rotates in the opposite direction. This mechanism allows the spacecraft to change or maintain attitude without the need for external forces. The attitude control is achieved based on the described operation: when a disturbance changes the platform's attitude, the wheel accelerates in the opposite direction to resist the rotation and restore the desired orientation.

Mathematical Modeling: The angular momentum H_W of the reaction wheel is given by: $H_W = I_W * \omega_W(t)$ where I_W the moment of inertia of the reaction wheel. The moment of inertia is dependent on the mass distribution and geometry of the reaction wheel. Specifically, in our design we will have a partially hollowed disk with concentrated masses placed along its rim to maximize the moment of inertia and minimize total mass. The exact value will be experimentally determined. Taking the derivative of H_W we get:

$$\dot{H}_W = I_W \dot{\omega}_W(t) \quad (1)$$

According to Euler's equations and considering static and dynamic frictions as

$$\tau = I_W \dot{\omega}_W - \tau_f \quad (2)$$

This models the fundamental dynamics of the system's rotation, based on Euler's equations.

Quantum-matrix versions of Lyapunov and Riccati Control Barrier differential equations will be implemented, improving

nonlinear response and runtime optimality. The equations include:

- Quaternion kinematics (attitude propagation)
- Rigid-body rotational dynamics (Euler's equations)
- Reaction wheel dynamics
- Control Lyapunov-Barrier Function (CLBF)

B. Control Strategy

PID Controller:The most commonly implemented controller for reaction wheels is the PID, due to both simplicity and robustness. The block diagram of the single-axis attitude control is shown in [Figure 1].

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the single-axis attitude control - PID

Computes torque based on attitude error:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (3)$$

where $e(t) = \text{Desired Angle} - \text{Measured angle}$ is the attitude error and K_p , K_i , K_d are the proportional, integral and derivative gains respectively.

C. Quantum Computing Terms

- 1) Quantum qubits: bits of information that exist in the Bloch sphere as a superposition of classical bit values 0,1.
- 2) Variational Quantum Circuits (VQCs): are parametrized quantum circuits trained by a classical optimization algorithm that makes queries to the quantum system [14]. They have grown to be a renowned method for quantum circuit realisation for near-term quantum devices.
- 3) Quantum Control Algorithms (e.g., QPSO, AHQSOA): are control strategies inspired by quantum computing principles, such as superposition and stochastic exploration. They extend classical methods by enabling adaptive, probabilistic, and multi-variable optimization in real time. Examples include Quantum Particle Swarm Optimization (QPSO) and Adaptive Hybrid Quantum Swarm Optimization Algorithm (AHQSOA) [5], which dynamically adjust control parameters to improve convergence, robustness, and stability under nonlinear or uncertain system dynamics [3], [6].
- 4) Control Lyapunov Function (CLF) - Control Barrier Function (CBF): that we will use for the quantum controller.

CLF:

$$V(q, \omega) = \frac{1}{2} \omega^T I \omega + k(1 - q_0), \dot{V} + cV \leq 0 \quad (4)$$

CBF:

$$h_i(\omega_{rw,i}, i) = \omega_{max} - |\omega_{rw,i}|, \dot{h}_i + \gamma h_i \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

- 5) Quantum Emulation on classical hardware (FPGAs): refers to the process of mimicking the behavior of quantum algorithms on classical hardware, such as FPGAs, without requiring actual quantum processors. It allows quantum-inspired methods—like variational circuits or stochastic control algorithms—to be tested and deployed in real-time systems, providing adaptability and robustness benefits while remaining compatible with existing platforms.

III. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

A. Challenges

- **Limitations of PID control under disturbances:** PID controllers are widely used for satellite attitude control due to their simplicity, but, as linear and reactive algorithms struggle under nonlinear dynamics, since they are inadaptable [3]. They are purely reactive, neglecting the system's history and dynamics. Under actuator saturation or sensor faults, these linear controllers make the system prone to unpredictable behavior. In suborbital flights disturbances such as residual accelerations, vibrations, thermal stresses, actuator saturation and sensor faults can inject unpredictable noise, leading to degraded or unstable performance [1], [7].
- **Latency and bandwidth constraints:** CubeSats and small satellites increasingly face latency and bandwidth constraints, which become more disruptive as mission complexity grows. For example, suborbital flights prevent continuous ground support, making for reliable onboard autonomy [8]. Modern space experiments demand intelligent onboard processing, since transmitting all data to Earth is often infeasible. Smart compression algorithms are of great importance in such instances. In the REXUS sounding rocket flight, these challenges are evident: In the telemetry the total PCM data stream is limited to 500kbit/s for all payloads, while the RS-422 interface provides an effective baud rate of 30 kbits/s. Furthermore, previous missions have reported latencies up to 50ms, data losses during launch and re-entry and unexpected communication dropouts. All these, make necessary an onboard processing compression.
- **Energy, thermal and computational limitations:** High performance CPUs and GPUs can execute advanced control algorithms, but they consume significant power and often exceed the thermal and energy budgets of small spacecrafts [4]. As shown in [Figure 2], FPGA-based quantum emulation achieves significantly lower execution times compared to CPU-based simulations. This demands rethinking computing platforms that combine low-power computation and enhanced performance in latency-sensitive aerospace applications.

- **Immaturity of quantum hardware:** Quantum technologies gain tremendous momentum generally [9] and in aerospace [10], [11]. However, quantum hardware requires a non-sensible budget, increases spatial constraints, while factors like cryogenic cooling and radiation sensitivity make it impractical for space missions yet.

B. Solutions

StarQuantrol is designed to address the above challenges by testing a quantum-inspired control algorithm on a reaction wheel (RW) platform under real suborbital flight conditions. Each solution is directly linked to a key aerospace bottleneck:

- 1) **Overcoming PID limitations with quantum-inspired algorithms:** Classical PID controllers provide stability in linear and reactive environments, but they fail to adapt under nonlinear dynamics or unpredictable disturbances, typical during a suborbital flight. Quantum-inspired algorithms like Quantum Particle Swarm Optimization (QPSO) introduce stochastic adaptation and dynamic parameter tuning. This enables faster convergence, resilience to noise and robust stabilization under uncertain dynamics [3]. Adaptive hybrid variants like AHQSOA further improve robustness by dynamically adjusting control gains in real time. In StarQuantrol, the quantum controllers are directly compared to classical PID on a reaction wheel platform, allowing an evaluation of their performance.

Fig. 2. CubeSat Satellite Model affected by External Disturbances and White Noise. [8]

- 2) **Reducing bandwidth via onboard compression on FPGA:** Suborbital flights and CubeSats suffer from

strict downlink limitations. Onboard FPGA-based compression and anomaly-preserving feature extraction reduce transmission volume while ensuring that critical information, such as anomalies or fault signatures, is prioritized. Implementing these processes directly on FPGA enables real-time, energy efficient data handling. One probable algorithm is LZ4, a fast, lossless data compression algorithm that reduces file size while preserving all original data (1.5-2.0 compression rate) [12].

- 3) **Power-efficient real-time FPGA execution:** By embedding quantum-inspired control and compression pipelines on a low-power FPGA, StarQuantrol delivers real-time execution at lower energy costs. FPGAs provide predictable execution latency and efficient data processing, making them a compelling alternative to GPUs and CPUs.
- 4) **Bridging quantum hardware and space technology:** Quantum processors are unsuitable for space missions due to infrastructure and cooling requirements. StarQuantrol demonstrates a quantum-inspired emulation on FPGA: it reproduces the adaptability and robustness of quantum methods in deployable hardware, validating quantum-inspired control strategies in a real suborbital environment.

Fig. 3. Experiment Block Diagram

IV. USAGE SCENARIOS

StarQuantrol demonstrates practical application of quantum-inspired methods in space systems, at a time when quantum computing for aerospace is still at an early stage.

- **CubeSat Attitude Control in LEO:** Maintaining pointing stability during eclipse transitions or payload slews using a quantum-inspired FPGA controller while detecting anomalies in real time.
- **Onboard Data Compression for Earth Observation:** Efficient FPGA-based compression and anomaly-preserving feature extraction allow priority transmission of critical data while storing bulk data for later recovery.

- **Autonomous Operations During Communication Blackouts:** FPGA platform ensures spacecraft stability and safety during periods without ground contact [10].

V. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

StarQuantrol aims to answer three critical questions:

- 1) To what degree can FPGA-based quantum controllers replace traditional PID controllers under suborbital flight conditions?
- 2) Can quantum controllers exhibit significant improvements in orientation accuracy, signal robustness, stability, and efficiency compared to traditional solutions?
- 3) Is the resolution of the system's differential representation faster using quantum-inspired methods compared to classical approximation methods?

VI. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

Our experiment was initially designed for REXUS flight, StarQuantrol, is a compact electromechanical platform designed to evaluate quantum-inspired control against a classical PID baseline during a suborbital flight. The mechanical part of the payload is a reaction wheel platform designed to demonstrate attitude control, with orientation measured by an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). A STM32 Nucleo microcontroller interfaces with the sensors and actuators, running a classical PID controller that serves as the benchmark for comparison. To complement this baseline, StarQuantrol implements and emulates quantum control algorithms, specifically Variational Quantum Circuits (VQC), on a custom FPGA-based quantum-classical control emulator designed for space conditions. Logical qubits are encoded and sensor data is processed in real time by a decoding unit on a Xilinx FPGA. As for the encoding, it is planned to be realized as a matrix accumulation in a fast, compressed way, like a sparse matrix transform. Environmental factors, such as temperature fluctuations and radiation events, are emulated to test adaptive behavior. The microcontroller will also ensure the serial connection required for smooth sensor integration and actuator control.

For the control part of the mechanism, an important technique of implementation is SVDD (Unsupervised Anomaly Detection) [13]. This module will be associated with adapting to the non-linearity of the system, taking note of any anomalies and having to record the disturbances of the sub-orbital environment without being costly in training mechanisms, disturbance simulations or high latency in data set loading. High-level quantum circuits are constructed in Qiskit for modeling and subsequently compiled into Verilog via a custom pipeline, mapping quantum gates, stabilizer measurements, and decision-making onto classical hardware. The custom dashboard logs system responses under various fault conditions, allowing detailed analysis efficiency under timing and hardware constraints. The FPGA will be connected to the brushless DC motor (BLDC) through an Electronic Speed Controller (ESC). The BLDC will be coupled to the reaction wheel, generating the proper angular momentum in order to achieve attitude control. An encoder will be used to measure

the motor's angular velocity and position and provide feedback to the FPGA and the Nucleo board respectively, each to their own slot of the feedback loop, using an interrupt-base routine. The FPGA will provide the reaction wheel with control signals either from the quantum-inspired algorithm or the PID. The quantum-inspired control data will be generated by the FPGA itself, whereas the PID control data will be computed by the STM32 microcontroller and will be transmitted to the FPGA. The data from both control algorithms will be also stored locally for post-experiment analysis.

A. Hardware

Reaction wheel platform, STM32 Nucleo microcontroller, Xilinx FPGA, BLDC motor with ESC, encoder, IMU.

B. Software / Control

Classical PID baseline; quantum-inspired control implemented on FPGA via VQC emulation; SVDD anomaly detection.

C. Workflow Phases

- 1) **Structures & Mechanisms:** Design and stress-test the mechanical platform, including thermal loads and vibration characteristics.
- 2) **Algorithm Prototyping:** Develop and prototype quantum-inspired control and compression algorithms in Qiskit; implement PID baseline.
- 3) **FPGA Hardware-in-the-Loop Implementation:** Integrate quantum-inspired control onto FPGA, test on 3D-printed reaction wheel.
- 4) **Sensor Fusion and Integration:** Full integration into a closed-loop system.
- 5) **ESA Experiment Campaigns:** Partial space-like condition testing in parabolic flights, drop towers, radiation chambers.
- 6) **End-to-End System Verification:** Thermal, radiation, vibration simulations; emulate space-like environments.
- 7) **Payload Deployment & Flight Demonstration:** Sub-orbital flight operating both PID and quantum-inspired controllers; downlink key metrics and log full system data onboard.

VII. DATA COLLECTION

A. Metrics

We will collect detailed control-performance metrics and system-health data under space-like conditions, to evaluate whether quantum control can outperform PID controllers under real suborbital flight conditions. Key measurements include:

- Unprocessed sensor data: Attitude data from IMU, including orientation, angular rates and linear accelerations; Reaction wheel kinematic data such as wheel speed, commanded set-point and power draw; Controller outputs, including PID terms and quantum-inspired parameters.
- Knowledge-Integrated Parameters (KIPs) representing system responses to real-time control corrections.

FPGA resource usage (logic elements, memory blocks, routing); Bandwidth and latency of the control-feedback loop under real-time sensor integration; Orientation accuracy and residual error; Robustness indicators: point stability and response to injected disturbances; Compression-like metric: quantify the reduction of the data size from performing the data compression and classification algorithms on them.

In addition to these scientific measurements we will record system-health data to verify the correct operation of the payload. This includes board and motor temperatures, supply voltages and currents, FPGA resource usage and communication statistics. These measurements are essential for validating payload operation and for correlating anomalies with environmental or hardware conditions.

VIII. MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGIES

Measurements will be taken with a combination of onboard sensors, controller outputs and FPGA diagnostics. Some of the data will be logged locally, while selected performance metrics will be downlinked in real time during flight.

- Sensors and raw data acquisition:
The IMU will provide orientation, angular rates and linear accelerations.
The encoder will be responsible for motor serial communication and speed/positional control of the motor connected to the wheel. Controller outputs:
The STM32 microcontroller will record PID terms.
The FPGA platform will log quantum-inspired parameters, related weights and gate outlines.
- System-health data:
Power consumption, currents drawn (complementary usage of XPE AMD Xilinx Power Consumption tool, for comparison to the expected amount of power),
Board temperatures, wheel overheating,
Downlink, Bit error rate (BER).
Watchdog status (dropped and if so, how many times, was its recovery enabled), Latency statistics and, Actual convergence rates of the algorithms.

A. Data Handling

The collected data will serve both scientific and engineering purposes, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the experiment's objectives. The expected outcomes and use of the data are:

- Performance Benchmarking Compare the quantum-inspired control algorithms with the classical PID baseline under suborbital flight conditions; Quantify improvements in orientation accuracy, convergence rates, robustness to disturbances, and stability margins.
- Validation of FPGA-based Autonomy Assess the feasibility of low-power, real-time FPGA platforms for advanced control and data handling in space; Demonstrate that quantum emulations on classical hardware can run efficiently on classical hardware, bridging the gap between

today's embedded systems and future quantum processors.

- Bandwidth and Data Handling Efficiency Evaluate the efficiency of onboard compression and anomaly detection in reducing downlink requirements without loss of mission-critical information; Establish methodologies for prioritizing essential data during communication-constrained operations.
- System Health and Reliability Insights Correlate anomalies in performance with environmental and hardware conditions (temperature fluctuations, power draw, vibration exposure, residual accelerations).
- Contribution to Future Missions Provide experimental evidence that quantum-inspired methods can enhance satellite and robotic autonomy in realistic environments; Inform the design of future CubeSat and ESA missions, where cost, mass, energy, and reliability constraints demand innovative control strategies.

The outcomes will be documented in a Final Experiment Report, accompanied by data sets, pareto plots (80-20 principle), performance analyses, and recommendations for scalability to operational space systems.

IX. INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

Supported by:

- CSLab, NTUA: Dr. Dionisis Pnevmatikatos
- CSLab, NTUA: PhD candidate Panagiotis Miliadis
- CSLab, NTUA: PhD candidate Konstantinos Papadopoulos
- SAMPS, NTUA: Dr. Ioannis Theodanis
- Control and Robotics Lab, NTUA: Dr. Ioannis Kordonis
- National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos"
- Project Management Mentorship: Dr. Antonios Livieratos, NKUA

X. MECHANICS

The experimental setup consists of a single-axis reaction-wheel platform designed to compare classical PID control with a quantum-inspired controller implemented on an FPGA. A brushless DC motor (BLDC) drives a precision reaction wheel whose speed and position are monitored by an encoder, while an IMU provides attitude and angular rate measurements. A STM32 Nucleo microcontroller runs the PID controller and handles supervisory tasks and a Xilinx FPGA executes the quantum-inspired control algorithm and data compression. Both controllers operate in closed-loop mode, with sensor data logged to an SD card and summarized telemetry transmitted for downlink. The system is powered by the REXUS 28 V line through DC-DC converters and a dedicated motor battery. All components are mounted on a compact aluminum frame. See Figure 4: Block Diagram of the experiment

XI. ELECTRICS / ELECTRONICS

The power supply will be necessary to power our reaction wheel system. We will use a DC-DC converter to power the FPGA and STM32 Nucleo respectively, and a DC-DC buck

Fig. 4. CAD design of the RW

Fig. 5. CAD design of the RW'

charger to charge the NiMh battery that will power our BLDC motor.

Voltage	Kv (RPM / Volt)	Resistance	No-Load Current	Reduction Ratio	Gearhead Efficiency	
24	V	182	0.288 Ω	0.493 A	0	85 %

AmpFlow Motor Calculations

Fig. 6. AmpFlow motor power calculator and robotic performance characteristics

More information about the battery is listed in the next section. This configuration is necessary as the BLDC motor and its controller may draw up to 5.38A continuous current, exceeding the 3A maximum of the REXUS service system.

We are going to use an additional NiMh battery to power the BLDC motor and its controller. The battery must contain 20 cells of 1.2V to achieve the nominal voltage of 24V. The separate battery is needed, and it is used as a storage device in order to provide the needed current, without affecting the REXUS power system. The motor may draw up to 5.38A current continuously, which exceeds the current draw limits of the REXUS service system; therefore it could not be powered directly from it. For charging we are going to use the 28VDC power line from the REXUS service system, along with an DC-DC buck charger set to draw 1A CC/CV, respecting the limits of the REXUS service system. The battery pack will also include a BMS circuit for overcharge and overcurrent protection.

A. Power consumption estimation

The power consumption of your experiment is estimated to be: 13.50Wh. We drew this conclusion due to the estimated BLDC motor (insert model), the (FPGA) Xilinx Power Estimator (XPE) AMD tool, alongside the Nucleo microcontroller and other electronics. The motor (suggested model: EC 60 flat Ø60 mm, brushless, 100 W, with Hall sensors) will require around 80W = 13.3Wh of power, in maximum torque [Figure 4]. As the results from the XPE estimator showcase (see drawings section) [Figures 7,8], the FPGA platform we will most likely use will be a mid-range one, in order to minimize the thermal results from its function and the module's conditions under sub-orbital flight, while making it cost-effective (potential model: Zync UltraScale++ - MPSoc, EG device). It is chosen based on the following criteria: computational power, power optimization and I/O flexibility. Thus, the FPGA will require around 0.13Wh making it ideal for rapid computations and low-energy consumption during the mission.

The Nucleo board STM32, alongside the sensors (IMU,

Fig. 7. Xilinx Power Estimator Tool - Synopsis of early estimation for FPGA power consumption

Encoder) fused into the embedded system are expected to

